

Modelling and Simulation of Integrated Renewable Energy System

¹Korla Praveen, ²K Sai Krishna, ³V Nirmala, ⁴S Manish, ⁵M Prasad, ⁶Dr T S Kishore

^{1,2,3,4,5} B Tech Student, ⁶Professor

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, GMR Institute of Technology, Vizianagaram District, A.P, India

Abstract— Power consumption is increasing in today's period of industrialization and urbanization. In the current scenario, Global annual energy consumption is 24.4K Terawatt-hours. This is around 2.5 times the amount consumed in 1981. As a result of its reliance on traditional sources, it is responsible for around 25% of global greenhouse gas emissions and other variant pollutants. Electricity usage is predicted to rise by roughly 2.1% per year through 2040, because of causes such as technological advancement and population expansion. Conventional sources of energy such as fossil fuels, nuclear power, and hydroelectricity are overexploited and unsustainable. It generates many harmful gases and has an impact on the climate. As a result, we are shifting to cleaner sources such as Renewable Energy Sources (RES), etc. These energy sources are sustainable, dependable, clean, and cost-effective, but they have drawbacks such as intermittency, storage, and cost. Hence in this project, we are integrating two renewable energy sources, namely IRES, to enhance the power system. The modelling and simulation of an integrated renewable energy system (IRES) is carried out and tested utilizing the MATLAB Simulink program.

Index Terms— Industrialization, Urbanization, Emission, Renewable Energy Sources, Intermittency, Integrated Renewable Energy Sources

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of the global economy and population is driving an increasing demand for energy. Currently, this demand is primarily met through the heavy reliance on fossil fuels, such as coal and oil. However, this reliance has severe environmental consequences, including the release of greenhouse gases and air pollution. To ensure a sustainable future, there is a growing need to transition towards cleaner and renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and hydropower. This shift not only addresses environmental concerns but also enhances energy security and global infrastructure resilience.[1] Despite the urgent need to transition to renewable energy sources, the detrimental impact of fossil fuels on human life persists. Urgent measures are required to aggressively promote the development of non-hydroelectric renewable energy sources. Solar and wind energy, known for their efficiency and environmental friendliness, have gained significant global attention and adoption. However, it's essential to recognize that wind and solar power generation can be highly variable and uncontrollable. [2-3] To address this issue and ensure a stable energy supply, effective energy storage systems are crucial. These systems play a pivotal role in mitigating power fluctuations associated with renewable energy sources, ultimately enhancing their reliability and integration into the broader energy grid.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Shukla et. al [1] gave a complete study on the modeling and simulation of a photovoltaic grid-connected system, emphasizing the necessity of supervision and control algorithms for PV system applications. The paper presents a comprehensive study on the modelling and simulation of a photovoltaic grid-connected system, highlighting the importance of supervision and control algorithms for PV system applications. A. Chouder et.al [2] said that the research paper provides a comprehensive evaluation of existing photovoltaic simulation software available to date. In addition, the study introduces the Solar Design tool, which focuses on online design for solar electric grid-tied systems and provides two design techniques. T. V. V. S. Lakshmi et.al [3] described an outstanding method for mathematically modeling a single cell solid oxide fuel cell with MATLAB/Simulink. The paper presents a remarkable approach for mathematically modelling a single cell solid oxide fuel cell using MATLAB/Simulink. The model considers transfer functions to calculate partial pressures of hydrogen, oxygen, and water, while accounting for activation, concentration, and ohmic losses to obtain better fuel cell characteristics. S. Guo et.al [4] stated that the term "multi-objective capacity optimization of wind-photovoltaic-thermal energy storage hybrid power system with electric heater" refers to a research project aimed at enhancing the performance and efficiency of a hybrid renewable energy system. "The multi-objective capacity optimization of wind-photovoltaic-thermal energy storage hybrid power system with electric heater" suggests a research study focused on improving the performance and efficiency of a hybrid renewable energy system. This system likely combines wind, photovoltaic (solar), and thermal energy sources, along with energy storage capabilities and an electric heater component. Ceylan and Devrim [5], is said that the study explores the design and optimization of a hybrid renewable energy system using PV, Electrolyze, and PEMFC to meet the electricity and heating needs of a greenhouse. The results revealed that the suggested hybrid system is a cost-effective and self-sustaining solution for freestanding greenhouse applications, demonstrating the capabilities of hybrid renewable energy systems to improve energy efficiency and reliability in a variety of scenarios.

III. MODELLING OF SOLAR PV SYSTEM

A solar cell operates on the principle of a p-n junction embedded within a thin semiconductor layer or wafer.[3] This ingenious device serves as a direct converter of solar energy's electromagnetic radiation into usable electric power, thanks to the photovoltaic effect. When exposed to sunlight, it's the photons carrying energy levels exceeding the semiconductor's specific band-gap energy that play a pivotal role.

Fig1: Equivalent Circuit of Photovoltaic cell

A standard equivalent circuit for a photovoltaic (PV) model includes components such as photocurrent, a diode, a parallel resistor representing leakage current, and a series resistor representing internal resistance to current flow.[4]The mathematical representation of a solar cell's voltage-current relationship is typically described using this equivalent circuit.

$$I_{pv} = N_p * I_{ph} - N_p Y I_{rs} \left(\exp \left[\frac{Qv_0}{TKAN_s} \right] - 1 \right) \tag{1}$$

Fig2: Simulation model of PV system

IV. MODELLING OF WIND ENERGY SYSTEM

In recent years, the use of wind energy for electricity generation has increased., driven by the need to provide a sustainable power supply to consumers.[5] This approach offers several advantages, including high efficiency, environmental friendliness (as it produces no pollution), cost-effectiveness, and the absence of fuel requirements.[6] The wind energy conversion system encompasses a complex interplay of 26 distinct components, falling into the categories of aerodynamics, mechanics, and electronics. The mechanical energy output from the gearbox is then directed towards a generator, where it is converted into electrical energy.

Hence, to begin with energy conversion process, the initial process is to identify the amount of energy present in wind, i.e., kinetic energy. The wind's kinetic energy is expressed as

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 \tag{2}$$

[7] The available power from the wind, denoted as P_{wind} and measured in kilograms per cubic meter (kg/m^3), is dependent on the swept area of the rotor blades represented by A , the air density ρ , and the wind speed V in meters per second (m/s). The wind turbine's actual power, which is the energy effectively harnessed, is determined by this equation, as well as the mechanical torque generated by the wind turbine.

$$P_{wt} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) \tag{3}$$

$$T_{wt} = \frac{P_{wt}}{\omega} \tag{4}$$

Fig 3: Simulink model of wind energy system

V. MODELLING OF FUEL CELL

Fuel cells represent a highly promising future technology for renewable energy-based power generation, and they come with several significant advantages, including sustainability, reliability, and the delivery of high-quality power.[8][2] One of the most noteworthy aspects of fuel cells is their ability to operate without emitting harmful pollutants like nitrogen oxides, carbon compounds, or sulfur derivatives, making them an environmentally friendly choice. Among the various types of fuel cells, the proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell stands out as particularly advantageous.

The PEM fuel cell's output voltage is represented as

$$V_{CELL} = E_n - V_{act} - V_{ohmic} - V_{con} \tag{5}$$

The potential of the fuel cell is obtained where E_n Nernst voltage is present.

Fig4: Simulink model of fuel system

**VI. ALGORITHM FOR TRACKING MAXIMUM POINT
PERTURB&OBSERVE METHOD**

Fig5: Perturb and Observe algorithm

The algorithm you're describing is a simplified version of a Perturb and Observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm. [9] This is one of the most commonly used MPPT techniques in photovoltaic systems due to its simplicity and effectiveness. Let's break down how this algorithm works

Perturbation: [10] This refers to making small adjustments to the operating parameters (voltage or current) of a photovoltaic (PV) module.

Monitoring Power Change: [11] After a perturbation is made, the algorithm observes how the power output of the PV module responds. An increase in power indicates that the module was not operating at its peak power point.

Fig6: Flowchart of perturb and observe algorithm

VII. MODELLING OF PROPOSED GRID CONNECTED SYSTEM

[13] A sophisticated system known as a micro-grid is made up of many different components, including solar photovoltaic (PV) panels, wind turbines, distributed energy sources based on micro-turbines, energy storage devices such as batteries, fuel cells, or flywheels, power electronic converters, and various types of electrical loads. [12] This system's main objective is to deliver electricity to isolated or rural areas through a single, controlled system. Notably, because they can operate in grid-connected and standalone modes, micro-grids offer flexibility in managing power supply.

Fig7: Block diagram of hybrid micro-grid

VIII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SIMULATION OUTPUTS OF SOLAR ENERGY SYSTEM

In the MATLAB/SIMULINK model, there is a system incorporating a 1.5 kW solar photovoltaic (PV) setup, a 1.5 kW wind energy conversion system using a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG), a 1.5 kW fuel cell based on a proton exchange membrane (PEM), and a 3 kW diesel generator. [13] Each of these systems is equipped with individual boost converters to amplify the output voltage and regulate power delivery to the load. These power sources are interconnected in parallel, sharing a common DC link bus with a voltage of 1000 volts. The DC link voltage is fed to an inverter, converting DC to AC power. The inverter's output is linked to the load through a three-phase circuit breaker under normal conditions. [14] If abnormal situations occur, the diesel generator connects to the load via another three-phase circuit breaker. An LC filter across the inverter helps filter out high-frequency harmonics from the inverter's output current. Additionally, the figure illustrates the output voltage, current, and power of the solar PV system.

Fig8: Output of voltage, current, power of Solar PV.

In the solar PV system, the open circuit voltage of 31 volts and short circuit current of 8.75 amps for each solar panel are designed. The entire solar PV system consists of four PV panels. [15] The solar output voltage is 124 volts, and the solar output current is 8.05 amps. Therefore, the power produced from the solar system is nearly 1000 watts.

SIMULATION OF FUEL CELL SYSTEM

Single-stack fuel cells operate within a stable voltage range of 26V to 36V while maintaining a constant fuel input. Individually, a fuel cell yields an output voltage between 0.5V to 0.9V. To enhance the output voltage, multiple fuel cells are combined in a series configuration.[16] In this particular setup, eight PEM fuel cell stacks are connected in series to achieve a total output of 102.4V. Consequently, the voltage output of the stacked fuel cells in this configuration amounts to 150V with a current of 10A,

resulting in an overall output power of 1024 watts. The figure depicts the output voltage of the fuel cell stack.

Fig9: Output of voltage, current, power of fuel cell.

This voltage is increased using a boost converter. The input voltage of the boost converter is 102.4 volts. To obtain the required output voltage for the PEM fuel cell stack, sufficient inductor and capacitor values are determined. The figure shows the output voltage, current, and power of the PEM fuel cell on the Y-axis, with time placed on the X-axis.

SIMULATION OF WIND ENERGY SYSTEM

[17]The wind energy system is created using a wind turbine based on a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG). The wind speed is modulated in increments, ranging from 18 m/s to 25 m/s, facilitated by a Staircase generator. Consequently, the system's output is inherently variable, influenced by the altering wind speeds experienced by the wind turbine.[18] The variability in the wind system's outputs is a direct result of the fluctuations in wind speed encountered by the turbine. The AC output showcases a voltage of 500 volts and a current of 5 amps within this wind power system, as depicted in the provided figure.

Fig10: Output of voltage, current, power of wind system.

[20] To elevate the rectified DC voltage to meet the desired output voltage level, a boost converter is employed. The output voltage and current's magnitude fluctuates with shifts in wind speed, impacting their frequency as well. Correspondingly, alterations in wind speed lead to variations in the wind power system's output power, mirroring the changes in the output voltage. The depicted Figure 4.2.2 illustrates the DC output voltage, current, and power of the wind power system, presenting voltage, current, and power on the Y-axis and time on the X-axis.

SIMULATION OF INTEGRATED RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEM

[19] Effective load management and a decrease in power losses within the grid are made possible by the simulation of an integrated renewable energy system made up of fuel cell, solar, and wind technologies. The simulation's outcomes demonstrate a thorough comprehension of this integration. The integrated system's combined output of voltage and current is shown on the graph, demonstrating how it supplies electricity to the linked load and the grid simultaneously. This simulation highlights how renewable energy sources may work together to improve grid stability, increase energy sustainability, and meet changing energy needs while having the least possible negative environmental effect.

Fig11: Output of voltage, current, power of Integrated Renewable Energy system.

IX. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a MATLAB/Simulink model illustrating the integration of renewable energy sources, specifically wind, solar, and fuel cell systems, connected to the grid. Within this model, a Voltage Source controller is meticulously designed using MATLAB/Simulink to effectively regulate a three-phase grid-connected voltage source inverter. The objective of this integration, termed the Integrated Renewable Energy System (IRES), is to notably enhance power quality while ensuring a consistent and uninterrupted power supply that aligns with varying load demands. IRES emerges as an economical and viable solution for powering rural and remote areas. Its operational efficacy is evident in maintaining stable power supply even in the face of faults or fluctuations in renewable energy outputs or within the grid. This stability is facilitated by the IRES's inherent capacity to promptly address deviations, displaying minimal settling time and delivering a steady output. Moreover, it significantly reduces power fluctuations, ensuring a smoother performance of the entire system. One of the key advantages of the IRES model lies in its ability to contribute to the overall socio-economic advancement of communities reliant on isolated loads. By offering reliable and steady power, it elevates living standards, fuels economic growth, and fosters a more sustainable environment. Overall, the integration of renewable energy sources through the IRES model showcases the potential to revolutionize the power sector, providing a roadmap towards a greener and more energy-efficient future.

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